

A, B, *C. alopecuroides*. C, D, *C. aphanolepis*. E, F, *C. benkei*. G, H, *C. brownii*. I, J, *C. confertiflora*.
A, C, E, G, I, overview, scale bar=1 mm. B, D, F, H, surface ornamentation, scale bar=10 μm.

A, B, C. *dispalata*. C, D, *doniana-1*. E, F, *doniana-2*. G, H, *honglinii*. I, J, *huashanica*.
 A, C, E, G, I, overview, scale bar=1 mm. B, D, F, H, surface ornamentation, scale bar=10 μ m.

A, B, C, *ischnostachya*. C, D, *C. japonica-1*. E, F, *C. japonica-2*. G, H, *C. liui*. I, J, *C. nemostachys*.
A, C, E, G, I, overview, scale bar=1 mm. B, D, F, H, surface ornamentation, scale bar=10 μ m.

A, B, *C. nipposinica*. C, D, *C. obliquicarpa*. E, F, *C. olivacea*. G, H, *C. persistens*. I, J, *C. planiculmis*. A, C, E, G, I, overview, scale bar=1 mm. B, D, F, H, surface ornamentation, scale bar=10 μm.

A, B, *C. pseudoaphanolepis*. C, D, *C. pseudodispalata*. E, F, *C. purpureotincta*. G, H, *C. radicina*. I, J, *C. remotistachya*. A, C, E, G, I, overview, scale bar=1 mm. B, D, F, H, surface ornamentation, scale bar=10 μ m.

A, B, *C. retrofracta*. C, *C. sclerocarpa*. D, E, *C. sinoaristata*. F, *C. subglabra*. G, H, *C. submollicula*. I, J, *C. subtransversa*. A, C, D, F, G, I, overview, scale bar=1 mm. B, E, F, H, J, surface ornamentation, scale bar=10 μ m.

A, B, *C. transversa*. C, D, *C. tumida*. A, C, overview, scale bar=1 mm. B, D, surface ornamentation, scale bar=10 μm .